

1 **Unbiased discovery of genes required for pluripotency: CLDN6.**

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6 Qualities of the stem cells of the embryo or the gametes include pluripotency and totipotency. Pluripotency
7 as a quality that defines the embryonic stem cell is likely a process or entity distinguishable from the
8 multi-lineage differentiation capacity that defines the HSC. We separated hematopoietic stem and
9 embryonic stem programs for blind discovery of pluripotency-associated factors in the ES cell. We
10 describe identification of CLDN6 as a factor regulating or associated with pluripotency in the human
11 embryonic stem cell.

12 Citations

13 1. Kong, F.E., Li, G.M., Tang, Y.Q., Xi, S.Y., Loong, J.H.C., Li, M.M., Li, H.L., Cheng, W., Zhu, W.J.,
14 Mo, J.Q. and Gong, Y.F., 2021. Targeting tumor lineage plasticity in hepatocellular carcinoma using an
15 anti-CLDN6 antibody-drug conjugate. *Science Translational Medicine*, 13(579), p.eabb6282.

16 2. Zheng, A., Yuan, F., Li, Y., Zhu, F., Hou, P., Li, J., Song, X., Ding, M. and Deng, H., 2007.
17 Claudin-6 and claudin-9 function as additional coreceptors for hepatitis C virus. *Journal of virology*, 81(22),
18 pp.12465-12471.

19 3. Arabzadeh, A., Troy, T.C. and Turksen, K., 2006. Role of the Cldn6 cytoplasmic tail domain in
20 membrane targeting and epidermal differentiation in vivo. *Molecular and cellular biology*, 26(15),
21 pp.5876-5887.